

3 RESOURCES 2-FOOD

Coordinating Lead Authors:

Rachid Mrabet (Morocco), Robert Savé (Spain)

Lead Authors:

Andrea Toreti (Italy), Nuno Caiola (Spain), Mouad Chentouf (Morocco), Maria Carmen Llasat (Spain), Assem Abdelmonem Ahmed Mohamed (Egypt), Fabio G. Santeramo (Italy), Alberto Sanz-Cobena (Spain), Athanassios Tsikliras (Greece)

Contributing Authors:

Eduardo Aguilera (Spain), Luis Asin (Spain), Andrej Cegljar (Italy), Alejandro de Blas (Spain), Donna Dimarchopou-lou (Greece), Elena Georgopoulou (Greece), Luis Lassaletta (Spain), Androniki Pardalou (Greece), Giuseppe Scarcella (Italy), Marco Turco (Spain), Matteo Zampieri (Italy)

This chapter should be cited as: Mrabet R, Savé R, Toreti A, Caiola N, Chentouf M, Llasat MC, Mohamed AAA, Santeramo FG, Sanz-Cobena A, Tsikliras A 2020 Food. In: Climate and Environmental Change in the Mediterranean Basin – Current Situation and Risks for the Future. First Mediterranean Assessment Report [Cramer W, Guiot J, Marini K (eds.)] Union for the Mediterranean, Plan Bleu, UNEP/MAP, Marseille, France, pp. 237-264, doi:10.5281/zenodo.7101080.

Table of contents

3.2 Food	240
Executive summary.....	240
3.2.1 Past trends and current situation.....	241
3.2.1.1 <i>Demand for agricultural products, consumption and trade</i>	242
3.2.1.2 <i>Marine food resources</i>	245
3.2.1.3 <i>Observed impacts of extreme weather and climate events on food production</i>	246
3.2.1.4 <i>Food policy and economics</i>	246
3.2.2 Projections, vulnerabilities and risks.....	247
3.2.2.1 <i>Agricultural resources</i>	247
3.2.2.2 <i>Marine food resources</i>	249
3.2.3 Adaptation and mitigation.....	249
3.2.3.1 <i>Adaptation of the food system to environmental change</i>	249
3.2.3.2 <i>Mitigation of climate change drivers</i>	251
<i>Nitrogen fertilization optimization</i>	251
<i>Improved water management</i>	252
<i>Soil improvement</i>	252
3.2.3.3 <i>Synergies and trade-offs between adaptation and mitigation</i>	253
References	255
Information about authors	264

3.2 Food

Executive summary

Food production in the Mediterranean Basin, from both land and the sea, is impacted by climate change, more frequent and intense extreme events, jointly with land degradation, overfishing, ocean acidification and salinization of coastal soils. Climate extremes pose a threat to the entire agriculture sector. Extremes, such as heat stress, droughts but also floods, can cause crop yield losses/failures, crop quality reduction and impacts on livestock. Perturbations in the global agricultural markets may exacerbate the local impacts of climate change, especially because most Mediterranean countries are net importers of cereals and fodder/feeding products. Mostly due to unsustainable fishing, total fish landings in the Mediterranean Sea have declined by 28% from 1994 to 2017.

Climate projections show a decrease of water availability and an intensification of extremes in the Mediterranean region, and thus a higher risk for the agriculture sector. Crop yield reductions are projected for the next decades in most current areas of production and for most crops. The cultivation of some water demanding crops like maize or vegetables could become impossible in many Mediterranean regions if there will be no enough water for irrigation. This will potentially be worsened by emerging pests and pathogens, and

perturbations in the global food markets due to environmental crises elsewhere.

Sea level rise will also negatively affect the agriculture sector by its direct impact on agricultural areas and associated increasing soil salinity, which could be multiplied by three. Rice production in Egypt and Spain could be the most affected.

Climate change is projected to heavily affect marine resources in the next decades. Warmer temperatures, acidification and water pollution will likely reduce marine productivity, affect species distribution and trigger local extinction of more than 20% of exploited fish and marine invertebrates around 2050.

In agriculture, there are large possibilities for adaptation consisting mostly in changing farming practices and application of more sustainable methods, including agroecological strategies. Successful strategies for sustainable development and enhanced resilience to environmental change are based on combining different approaches, i.e., reduced tillage, varieties, rotational patterns, and crop diversity or diversification of income. Sectorial co-designed climate services will represent a key asset to reduce the risk linked to unfavorable climate conditions and extremes.

Figure 3.13 | Total agricultural land in the Mediterranean countries in 2016 (% with respect to the total land at country scale). Source: World Bank (accessed February 2020).

Figure 3.14 | Total irrigated land in the Mediterranean countries (latest reported value in % with respect to the agricultural land at the country scale). Source of data: World Bank Data (accessed February 2020).

Sustainable intensification of farming systems offers greenhouse gas mitigation options by nitrogen fertilization optimization, improved water management, higher storage of soil organic carbon and carbon sequestration both in annual and perennial cropping systems, management of crop residues and agroindustry by-products.

3.2.1 Past trends and current situation

The ensemble of the Mediterranean countries has approximately 877 million ha of land, of which about 28% is devoted to agriculture (*Fig. 3.13*). There is a pronounced spatial heterogeneity in the share of agricultural land, from 4% of Egypt to almost 76% of Syria (*Fig. 3.13*). The agriculture sector is characterized by a variety of different farm structures and agro-management practices combined with pronounced differences in environmental conditions, rendering substantial variation in agricultural inputs (e.g., nutrients, pesticides, water for irrigation) and outputs (e.g., crop yields). Irrigation is practised only on 8% of the Mediterranean agricultural land area (*Fig. 3.14*), however uncertainties characterize this value as data for several countries are neither available nor updated. Israel has the highest portion of agricultural land being irrigated (approx. 33%, *Fig. 3.14*).

The Mediterranean agriculture production is characterized by high spatial variability and differences (*Table 3.9*). Annual crops include cereals (e.g., wheat, maize, barley and rice), and

vegetables (e.g., potatoes and tomatoes). Together, wheat, maize, barley and rice cover, for almost all Mediterranean countries, more than 90% of the entire cereal production, with rice having a significant share (>3%) only in Egypt, Greece, North Macedonia, Portugal, Spain and Italy. Permanent crops consist of fruit, olives, grapes and dates. For cereals, France, Turkey, Egypt, Spain and Italy produce (2014-2018 average) about 66, 35, 23, 21, and 18 million t, respectively (*Table 3.9*). As for fruit and vegetable production, the highest values (15-22 million t for fruit, and 13-24 million t for vegetables) come from Egypt, Italy, Spain and Turkey (*Table 3.9*).

Although productivity has increased in recent decades, there are still large differences in the region, with for instance wheat yield ranging from approx. 1 to almost 7 t ha⁻¹ (FAO 2017). These differences are also reflected in the estimated yield gap for wheat, maize and barley (e.g., Mueller et al. 2012; Schils et al. 2018). Improved agro-management practices can contribute to close the gap in regions where large differences exist between potential and farm yield. As an example, Pala et al. (2011) found that wheat yields can be increased 1.6–2.5 times in Morocco, 1.7–2.0 times in Syria and 1.5–3.0 times in Turkey.

Large spatial differences also characterize the livestock subsector, with meat (beef and buffalo) production varying from 0.1 to 143.9x10⁴ t; while milk production varies from 0.4 to 262.7x10⁵ t (*Table 3.9*). Milk productivity also spans a vast range from

	Cereal	Fruit	Vegetables	Meat (beef & buffalo)	Milk
Albania	6.9	7.8	8.0	0.39	11.4
Algeria	40.4	67.6	63.4	1.57	35.8
Bosnia and Herzegovina	13.6	3.3	7.7	0.15	7.0
Bulgaria	92.5	4.9	4.6	0.18	11.3
Croatia	30.6	3.2	12.4	0.43	6.8
Cyprus	0.4	1.8	0.7	0.05	2.5
Egypt	229.7	150.8	158.2	7.89	51.6
France	662.6	92.2	52	14.39	262.7
Greece	38.5	40.5	25.2	0.43	19.4
Israel	2.9	13.8	14.9	1.29	15.4
Italy	175.8	175.3	125.9	7.75	119.3
Jordan	1.0	5.4	16.2	0.27	3.5
Lebanon	1.7	8.0	8.2	0.45	2.6
Libya	2.7	6.8	6.8	0.09	2.3
Malta	0.1	0.1	0.8	0.01	0.4
Montenegro	0.1	0.8	0.2	0.04	1.7
Morocco	84.7	57.3	40.3	2.61	23.9
North Macedonia	5.6	5.8	6.9	0.05	4.5
Palestine	0.5	1.2	6.4	0.08	1.6
Portugal	11.9	19.6	24.4	0.89	20.8
Serbia	95.2	16.5	8.5	0.69	16.0
Slovenia	6.2	2.1	0.9	0.34	6.4
Spain	211.6	192.7	128	6.32	80.2
Syria	31.4	25.1	17.9	0.70	22.3
Tunisia	17.8	20.9	30.3	0.59	13.8
Turkey	354.3	217.5	239.8	9.90	197.2
Kosovo	95.2	16.5	8.5	0.69	16.0

Table 3.9 | Production of cereals, fruit, vegetables, meat and milk in the Mediterranean countries, 2014-2018 average, 10⁵ tonnes. Data source: FAOSTAT (accessed February 2020).

800 kg animal⁻¹ in Libya to 5,500 kg animal⁻¹ in Slovenia. Overall, Mediterranean countries of the MENA region have an average milk productivity of 700 kg animal⁻¹, compared to 1,800 kg animal⁻¹ of the other countries and 2,300 kg animal⁻¹ for the EU countries in the region.

3.2.1.1 Demand for agricultural products, consumption and trade

Agricultural demand in the Mediterranean region is influenced by changing dietary patterns and by the socio-economic and political situation of each country, including population growth and import/export flows. In 2013, the Mediterranean diet has been recognized by UNESCO as intangible cultural heritage of humanity, involving not only food production, processing and consumption but

also social behaviour and community identity. Its low environmental impact and its importance for a sustainable future have been highlighted in many studies (Sofi et al. 2010; Capone et al. 2012; CIHEAM and FAO 2015). Recent studies indicate a diet transition affecting the Mediterranean countries and posing a threat for the preservation and enhancement of the Mediterranean diet (Bonaccio et al. 2012, 2014; CIHEAM and FAO 2015). These changes may further affect nutritional issues and human health in Mediterranean countries, where already malnutrition (characterized by the presence of significant percentage of overweight and underweight population) takes place.

The food system of the Mediterranean also contributes to the ecological deficit as estimated by Galli et al. (2015) and updated in the National Footprint Accounts 2019¹⁵. The amount and the

¹⁵ Global Footprint Network, <http://data.footprintnetwork.org/>

type of contribution are country dependent, and in some cases (e.g., Portugal, Greece, Spain, Malta, Croatia and Italy) characterized by a relevant component of meat, dairy and fish (Galli et al. 2017). Changes during the last decade (2000-2013) in meat consumption are not homogeneous in the Mediterranean region, with twelve countries show-

ing a significant increase, six having characterized by a significant decrease and the others having a stationary pattern. For fish, fourteen countries show a significant increase, only two a significant decrease and all others have a stationary pattern (Fig. 3.15).

Figure 3.15 | Meat and fish consumption (kg capita⁻¹ yr⁻¹) in Mediterranean countries from 2000 to 2013 (FAO 2017).

Trade patterns play a key role in the Mediterranean region, with most of the countries being net importer of cereal and fodder/feeding products (Fig. 3.16 and 3.17). Concerning cereal, four countries (Italy, Spain, Egypt, and Algeria) import 12-19 million t of cereal, while France exports about 29 million t (Fig. 3.16). As for fodder and feeding products, five Mediterranean countries import more than one million t, with Turkey reaching about 4.3 million t (Fig. 3.17). The current trade patterns have been reached by a profound transformation of the agricultural systems that has occurred in the last decades, often characterized by a decoupling of the crop and livestock producing systems (Lassaletta et al. 2014).

Overall, the Mediterranean region, in terms of nitrogen (N) import has moved towards a more unbalanced situation with most of the countries being net larger importer (Fig. 3.18) (Lassaletta et al. 2014; Sanz-Cobena et al. 2017). The decoupling of the crop and livestock producing systems caused a lower nutrient efficiency and issues associated with the lack of manure in cropping area and

excessive manure in livestock farms (Lassaletta et al. 2012; Sanz-Cobena et al. 2017). The excessive manure production is difficult to manage, and over-application in areas close to high-density livestock systems can severely affect the environment. As a consequence, a high risk of catchment pollution has been estimated and reported in some studies (Lassaletta et al. 2012; Romero et al. 2016).

The Mediterranean is among the oldest examples of strongly coupled human-environment system that has undergone very profound land/landscape changes driven by activities such as the agriculture and by the human-water interaction (Barton et al. 2010, 2016) (Section 4.3.1.1). Many factors have contributed to these changes in the Mediterranean, e.g., people’s mobility towards the coast and the urban areas, tourism expansion, industrialization, agriculture intensification (Bajocco et al. 2012; Niedertscheider and Erb 2014).

These changes have contributed to alter land quality, productivity and to degradation. Changes have not been homogeneous as very different

Figure 3.16 | Cereal trade patterns (average 2014-2017 values in tonnes x 10⁷) in the Mediterranean countries: import (deep blue) and export (light blue) contribution for each Mediterranean country (identified by the ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 code) (FAO 2017).

Figure 3.17 | Trade patterns in fodder and feeding products (average 2014-2017 values in tonnes x 10⁶) in the Mediterranean countries: import (deep blue) and export (light blue) contribution for each Mediterranean country (FAO 2017).

Figure 3.18 | Net protein fluxes (Gg N) of food and feed imported to the Mediterranean regions from the other countries in 2009. Green countries are net N exporters to the Mediterranean. Yellow/red countries are net N importing from the Mediterranean. Fluxes below 50 Gg N are not represented (adapted from Sanz-Cobena et al. 2017).

socio-economic conditions characterize the region as well as behavioural patterns in farming. For instance, in some areas of the western Mediterranean the abandonment of dryland farming, of farming activities in mountainous and/or re-mote regions, and the consequent afforestation modified the ecosystems and the services provided (Kauppi et al. 2006; Falcucci et al. 2007; Padilla et al. 2010). Abandonment of agricultural terraces in mountainous regions has in some cases also favored erosion processes and loss of fertile soil (Arnaez et al. 2011). Land competition has also played a key role in some regions of southern Mediterranean, e.g., Morocco (Debolini et al. 2015). Mobility towards urban areas, evolving economic conditions, modified productivity in agricultural areas of Mediterranean countries also contributed to shifts in the cultivated crops. In Crete (Greece), for instance, a transition from cereal production towards olive cultivation characterized the 20th century (Karamesouti et al. 2015). In some countries, urbanization has forced agricultural expansion towards marginal areas requiring higher management levels in terms of irrigation and fertilization (Abd-Elmabod et al. 2019).

3.2.1.2 Marine food resources

Mediterranean total fishery landings have been declining in the last years (Fig. 3.19) (Tsikliras et al. 2015; FAO 2018) and so are the reconstructed catches that included discarded, illegal and unreported and recreational fisheries catch (Pauly and Zeller 2016). Total landings of the entire Mediterranean Basin exceeded 1.16 million t in 1994 and declined to around 842,000 t in 2017, i.e., a decrease of 28% (Fig. 3.19).

While the peaks occurred relatively early in the central Mediterranean (~1985) and eastern Mediterranean (~1994), the landings peaked much later in the western Mediterranean (~2006) (Fig. 3.20). In 2017, the landings were relatively low: from 161,000 t in eastern Mediterranean to 325,000 t in central Mediterranean (Fig. 3.20). In 2017, the highest contribution to the total landings in the Mediterranean came from Italy (22%), followed by Algeria (12%), Tunisia (12%), and Spain (10%)¹⁶.

Small pelagic fishes constitute the vast majority of landings across the entire Mediterranean Sea, with European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) and

¹⁶ Data from FAO-GFCM, accessed March 2020. <http://www.fao.org/gfcm/en/>

Figure 3.19 | Total fish landings (tonnes) in the Mediterranean Sea from 1970 to 2017. Data source: FAO-GFCM¹⁶, accessed in March 2020.

European sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*) being the species with the most landings accounting for 34% of the 2014-2016 average annual landings (FAO 2018; Tsiakirias et al. 2019). The main pelagic fish species landed in the western Mediterranean are European anchovy, European sardine and sardinella nei (*Sardinella* spp.) accounting for 46% of the total landings (FAO 2018). In the Ionian part of central Mediterranean, European sardine, sardinella nei, jack and horse mackerel nei (*Trachurus* spp.), and common Pandora (*Pagellus erythrinus*) account for 30% of the total landings (FAO 2018). While in the Adriatic part of Central Mediterranean, landings of European sardine and anchovy reach 61% (FAO 2018). Finally, in the eastern Mediterranean, European sardine, anchovy and European sardine are again the main species landed accounting for 33% of the total landings (FAO 2018) (Sections 2.4.2, 4.1 and 4.2).

3.2.1.3 Observed impacts of extreme weather and climate events on food production

Extreme weather and climate events (such as floods, droughts, storms, heat waves and cold spells) pose a threat for agricultural production (Lesk et al. 2016; Zampieri et al. 2017; FAO 2018). The impacts of heat stress occurring in critical phenological phases can induce serious crop yield losses and quality reduction. In Italy, for instance, early heat waves have been associated to durum wheat yield losses occurred in the last decades (Fontana et al. 2015; Zampieri et al. 2017). In Greece, recent trends in extreme temperatures reduced cereal yields by 1.8-7.1% per degree increase in maximum temperatures (Mavromatis 2015). Also milk production and quality are affected by heat stress (Bernabucci et al. 2010, 2015; Gantner et al. 2017) as well as livestock fertility (de Rensis et al. 2015). Temperature changes during important

Figure 3.20 | Total Landings (t) from 1970 to 2017 in the Mediterranean Sea. Data source: FAO-GFCM¹⁶, accessed in March 2020.

phenological stages such as blossoming may affect yields of maize, alfalfa, apples, almonds and other crops (Savé et al. 2012; Funes et al. 2016; Díez-Palet et al. 2019).

The entire agriculture sector in the region is also heavily affected by drought events (Blauhut et al. 2015; Zampieri et al. 2017). Severe socio-economic impacts triggered by drought events were reported on Moroccan agriculture (Verner et al. 2018), with the events of 2007 (Schilling et al. 2012) and 2015-16 that caused heavy losses on wheat, citrus and olive production, posing a threat for the livestock sector. Severe droughts can also modify the rural landscape, preventing the adoption of new crops and ultimately forcing farmers to emigrate (Ruauadel and Morrison-Métois 2017). The costs and the risks associated with climate extremes are not only related to direct losses, such as crop failures, but also to a wide range of indirect effects triggered by market reactions to events occurring in other producing regions of the world (Chatzopoulos et al. 2019).

The Mediterranean is also a high fire-risk region, where fires are the cause of severe agricultural, economic and environmental losses and even human casualties (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al. 2013; Moritz et al. 2014; Bowman et al. 2017). The abandonment of agricultural land leads to an increased risk of forest fires due to the occupation of what were agricultural lands by forest and the bushes, and increasing the biomass available for burning as well as its spatial continuity. Conversely, some forest fires may be triggered for the creation of more pastures for livestock or farmland.

3.2.1.4 Food policy and economics

Agriculture and the entire food system are generally influenced by socio-economic conditions, also in Mediterranean countries. The strong

fluctuations in food markets are partly due to the characteristics of agricultural production itself (perishable products, climatic and health risks, seasonal production cycles, size of farms, distance from markets etc.), which, together with aspects of the overall economy, even of a geopolitical nature, can modify the food supply-demand balances (Reguant and Savé 2016). These conditions also endanger the capacity of Mediterranean countries to guarantee food security (Santeramo 2015). Among the Mediterranean countries, some in the southern and eastern shores have also suffered political instabilities and conflicts that have posed a challenge to the maintenance and development of the agriculture system (Tanyeri-Abur 2015; Petit and Le Grusse 2018).

The food system of the Mediterranean region in all its aspects (production, trade patterns, etc.) is under strong influence from the policies of high-income countries and, in particular, the European Union (Caracciolo et al. 2014). The tight links among Mediterranean countries imply that changes in the EU Common Agricultural Policy and in trade agreements may have important impacts on national agri-food sectors also outside the EU. For instance, the Euro-Mediterranean trade partnership between the EU and the southern and eastern Mediterranean non-EU countries (except for Syria and Libya, entered into force to promote trade and investments in the region) tends to influence market fundamentals in all Mediterranean countries. Furthermore, food quality standards and entry price mechanisms are very important for trade patterns (Cioffi et al. 2011; Santeramo and Cioffi 2012; Marquez-Ramos and Martinez-Gomez 2016; Bureau and Swinnen 2018).

Trade has prioritized the export of fruits and vegetables and has widened the production-consumption gap of cereals, which are the main food of the most vulnerable segments of the population in the southern and eastern parts of the region (Larson et al. 2002; Cioffi and Dell'Aquila 2004; García Martínez and Poole 2004). The vulnerability of the cereal sector has enhanced the impact of food price fluctuation on food security, which may have severe impacts (e.g., in terms of income level and income distribution) depending on the capacity of the countries to be self-sufficient (Caracciolo and Santeramo 2013).

Pasture based systems are becoming less competitive, due to the high labor costs (on-farm resources are being substituted with external inputs) promoting intensive livestock systems near urban areas (Malek et al. 2018). This has resulted in the increase in landless livestock systems in the Mediterranean region.

Mediterranean countries are vulnerable to price fluctuations on international markets due to their dependence on imports of basic foodstuffs. Worldwide phenomena (e.g., food crisis) have accentuated the structural weakness of the agricultural production model adopted by these countries, increasing social and political frustrations (Reguant and Savé 2016). In this context, it is worth to mention initiatives such as the Mediterranean Agricultural Market Information Network (MED-Amin)¹⁷ and the MedAgri platform¹⁸ from FAO, the European Bank and the World Bank. The drivers of price volatility are numerous and complex (Santeramo et al. 2018b), but it seems there is a consensus that arbitrage, and price discovery mechanisms tend to have a positive impact on price stabilization (Santeramo and Lamonaca 2019).

Access to agricultural technology is unequally distributed across countries of the Mediterranean area and is usually more accessible to farmers in the north-western part. It is also true that most developed countries tend to provide higher subsidies (at least in nominal terms) to their agricultural sector. The adoption of risk management strategies, and the access to credit are also very unequally distributed and generally lower in the developing countries of the Mediterranean area (Santeramo et al. 2014). These peculiarities allow to conclude that the less developed countries, among the Mediterranean ones are likely to be the most vulnerable to food security issues. On the other hand, investments on technology, on policies to promote the agri-food sector, and in particular to promote risk management strategies may prove effective mechanisms to enhance resilience to food security.

3.2.2 Projections, vulnerabilities and risks

3.2.2.1 Agricultural resources

Climate projections indicate significant warming and drying in the Mediterranean Basin, together with intensification of climate extremes such as

¹⁷ www.med-amin.org

¹⁸ www.medagri.org

drought and heat waves (Sections 2.2.5.2 and 2.2.4). Thus, severe impacts on the agriculture sector are to be expected if no adaptation and mitigation will take place. These impacts include changes in phenology and growing cycle of many crops (Trnka et al. 2011; Funes et al. 2016), combined with higher water demands due to enhanced evaporation (Savé et al. 2012; Girard et al. 2015; Saadi et al. 2015; Valverde et al. 2015; Phogat et al. 2018). The wheat growing period in Tunisia is expected to be shortened by 16 days for 2.5°C and by 30 days for 4°C (Mougou et al. 2011). Additional constraints include water scarcity (Section 3.1.4.1) (Vicente-Serrano et al. 2017, 2018) and soil salinity (Lagacherie et al. 2018; Phogat et al. 2018).

As a consequence, potential yields of crops and livestock yields are projected to decline in many areas due to climatic and other stress factors without adaptation. Several regions of the Mediterranean might entirely lose their suitability for growing specific crops (Ceglar et al. 2019). Crop yields in MENA countries are expected to decline by approx. 30% with 1.5-2°C warming in Jordan (Al-Bakri et al. 2011) and similarly in North Africa (Drine 2011) and up to 60% with 3-4°C warming (Schilling et al. 2012). Maize is projected to be among the most affected crops (Webber et al. 2018; Zampieri et al. 2019; Feyen et al. 2020), with significant yield decline of, e.g., 10-17% in Italy, Bulgaria, and Greece by the mid-century (2021-2050, under the business as usual RCP8.5 scenario and assuming the current agro-management will still be in place). Wheat yield losses are projected for some European countries in the Mediterranean region (5%-22% in 2021-2050 under the RCP8.5 scenario with no adaptation) (Feyen et al. 2020) associated with higher inter-annual variability and decrease resilience of the production (Zampieri et al. 2020). Reductions in wheat yield in case of no adaptation have been also reported for Algeria (Chourghal et al. 2016). However, reductions in water availability for maize irrigation could bring much bigger losses. Based on a meta-analysis of 16 studies available at the time, Waha et al. (2017) conclude that climate change constitutes a significant risk for crop yields across the MENA region (Fig. 3.21).

Soil and agro-management influence on the projected changes has also been reported for wheat yield in an Italian region, showing moderate yield increase as well as heavy decrease (63% in 2040-2070 under the A1B scenario, which is close to the relatively high scenario RCP6.0) (Bird et al. 2016) according to the soil type. While a strong dependence on water availability has been pointed out for tomato yield in Tunisia, where a 10% reduction in

Figure 3.21 | Crop yield changes in the MENA region based on a meta-analysis of 16 different studies (Waha et al. 2017).

water for irrigation could make some productions not feasible (Bird et al. 2016). In Tunisia, wheat yields may increase in some producing areas (Annabi et al. 2018). However, recurrent drought events may induce losses of approximately -50% in olive production, and the increase in floods could lead to a decrease of -13% in rainfed cereal production (Requier-Desjardins 2010). The effects of changes in precipitation regimes on olive production in the entire Mediterranean region were investigated by Tanasijevic et al. (2014) that pointed to the likely absolute need of irrigation in future olive cultivation. Large climate impacts have been also estimated (assuming no adaptation) for agriculture in Egypt increasing over time and triggering exceptional food price increases (McCarl et al. 2015). Sea level rise will also pose a threat to agriculture in Egypt leading to area losses and affecting, for instance, rice production (Chen et al. 2012; Sušnik et al. 2015). Similarly, heavy impacts of sea level rise and associated increased soil salinity (estimated to be three times the current one) on rice production have been estimated at the end of the century in Spain (Genua-Olmedo et al. 2016).

The increase in the atmospheric concentration of CO₂ could bring beneficial effects in terms of yield under optimal growing conditions (especially for C₃ crops such as wheat and barley) and could buffer some days more under drought conditions (Kimball 2016) but may also bring new nutritional challenges (Uddling et al. 2018; Asseng et al. 2019). Results also highlight the limited beneficial contribution of elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentration under pronounced water-stress conditions. Reductions in wheat protein yield by 5-10% have been estimat-

ed at some south-western locations of the basin (2040-2069 under the RCP8.5 scenario) (Asseng et al. 2019).

Concurrent and recurrent extremes, not fully considered in the current impact assessments, may well pose the main threat to the stability and the resilience of the Mediterranean production systems. Climate extremes occurring in other regions of the world may also trigger impacts through increased market volatility and price spikes (Chatzopoulos et al. 2019; Toreti et al. 2019). New and re-emerging pest and pathogens, usually not fully considered in impact assessments, may contribute to larger than estimated losses (Bebber et al. 2013, 2014). Another threat to food security and quality may be represented by mycotoxigenic fungal pathogens and higher level of contamination (Medina et al. 2017). Agriculture in the region may be also affected by increased risk of large fires, with a 34 to 140% rise according to the location and the scenario (Section 4.3.2.1).

3.2.2.2 Marine food resources

Projected climate change is also expected to heavily impact marine food resources, which are over-exploited already. Ocean warming, acidification, water pollution and constrained migration possibilities to cooler areas (due to sea enclosure) may lead to local extinction of up to 50% of exploited fish and marine invertebrates around 2050, affecting also endemic fishes, including commercial ones (e.g., Cheung et al. 2016) (Section 4.1.2.1). Pollution from anthropogenic activities also affects fish population, notably in the Nile delta, with potentially serious consequences on human food security.

Besides warming, marine ecosystems are also sensitive to increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentration due to its rapid dissolution in seawater, which causes alterations in the chemistry of inorganic carbon with a lower pH and higher concentration of carbonic ions (Doney et al. 2009). The carbonic ion is an essential element for organisms that depend on the deposition of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) through biomineralization for the formation of calcareous structures, such as the mollusk shells. If the biomineralization process does not occur properly, organisms reduce their growth rate and may present morphological anomalies that cause, for example, the loss of capacity of fixation to the substrate and diminishes feeding activity.

The joint effects of ocean warming and acidification may also include a number of biological alterations such as decreased ocean productivity

(Behrenfeld et al. 2006), reduced growth and survival of calcifying organisms (Hoegh-Guldberg et al. 2007), changes in species distributions, altered food dynamics (Vergés et al. 2014), and altered incidence of disease (Burge et al. 2014). These effects can be translated into a diminution of the abundance and, therefore, of the fisheries production. The affected activities would be both extractive fishing (shellfish, in this case) and aquaculture that is extensively used in coastal areas (Gazeau et al. 2014; Prado et al. 2016). The example of mollusks is perhaps the most quoted but we should not forget that other organisms are subject to biomineralization processes for the formation of the skeleton (e.g., fish), and thus, can also be negatively affected. The effects on habitats can also be quite important because at lower pH some plants can be affected directly or indirectly and even calcareous substrates of biological or mineral origin. All this has to be added to the benthic organisms with calcareous structures that are not commercial species but are the base of the food web for upper trophic groups.

To fully understand the potential effects of global change, it is important to focus on population bottlenecks, which are usually early developmental and reproductive stages (Thorson 1950). Survival of adult and juvenile bivalves shows little dependence on pCO₂ (Berge et al. 2006; Hendriks et al. 2010; Range et al. 2012), although increasing temperature may result in increasing mortality and metabolic rates (Basso et al. 2015). In contrast, gametes, embryos, and larvae are generally more sensitive to both temperature and elevated pCO₂ stress (Havenhand et al. 2008; Parker et al. 2009, 2010) because the deposition of CaCO₃ shells and skeletons begins in these stages (Kurihara et al. 2007). Yet, there is also a wide natural variability in pH ranges of seawater (7.5-8.5, with even lower values possible in semiconfined waters; Flecha et al. 2015) which may partly account for observed differences in the responses of calcifying organisms to acidification and complicates the generalization of patterns across species and ecosystems (Kurihara 2008).

3.2.3 Adaptation and mitigation

3.2.3.1 Adaptation of the food system to environmental change

The assessment of how climate change will affect crops is essential for policymakers, planners, farmers and all the other actors of the agriculture sector to develop, propose and implement adaptation and mitigation strategies at the local/regional

scale to make agriculture more resilient to changes (Liebig et al. 2016). For instance, future water availability and water demands put the current management model in question, so adaptation choices have to be necessarily developed (Iglesias and Garrote 2015; Ronco et al. 2017). The projected water scarcity and increase of drought events will limit adaptation actions based on irrigation. Under some scenarios combining climate change and population growth, half of the Mediterranean countries (mainly in the southern and eastern shores) are projected to be unable to cover irrigation water demands by the end of the century (Fader et al. 2016) (Section 3.1.5.2).

Crop distribution, diversity, varieties, rotation patterns, and agro-management represent key elements of adaptation strategies at the farm scale (Valverde et al. 2015; EEA 2019). Breeding and sowing new varieties water and heat stress tolerant (del Pozo et al. 2016, 2019; Hatfield and Dold 2019), adapting the crop calendar (Ronco et al. 2017), using optimal crop diversification (Lin 2011) could be all used as adaptation strategies. The inclusion or reintroduction of wild food plants, neglected and underutilized crops, also add to diversifying the agricultural portfolio of crops with potential resilience against climate change. North-south differences were estimated for the adaptive capacity in agriculture (Grasso and Feola 2012), mainly associated with soft factors (e.g., information) rather than with other more structural ones (such as technological and infrastructural perspective). Looking at the implemented adaptation strategies in the Mediterranean (Harmanny and Malek 2019), the most common ones are farming practices (diversify and change crop types, adjust crop rotation), water management (modify irrigation practices), and farm management (diversify source of income). The main drivers of such adaptation actions are water scarcity, environmental factors (climate change, soil degradation and erosion, sustainability), and socio-economic factors (Harmanny and Malek 2019).

Combining several actions can also lead to better results in terms of crop yield. Higher wheat yield under different water conditions in Lebanon were achieved by using a drought-tolerant variety, conservation tillage and precise irrigation during grain filling¹⁹. A higher degree of diversification, more varieties of the main crops, earlier sowing,

and hedgerow planting were also identified as actions to increase the resilience in a pilot farm project in southern France²⁰. Crop productivity (vines, corn, apples, lucerne) was increased using different agronomical practices to increase water availability by plants without increase water from irrigation in Spain²¹. Some strategies have also additional indirect benefits, such as soil organic carbon accrual due to agroforestry (Chatterjee et al. 2018), cover crops (Aguilera et al. 2013b; Vicente-Vicente et al. 2016), and local crop varieties with a higher residue and root biomass production (Carranza-Gallego et al. 2018) (Section 6.4). Improved soil erosion control, increasing soil fertility, retaining soil moisture and resource efficiency are the dominant drivers for conservation agriculture, organic farming and agroforestry (Lagacherie et al. 2018). Conservation agriculture represents a relatively widely adopted management system that aims to sustain long-term crop productivity and system's sustainability (Kassam et al. 2012). The environmental and economic benefits of no-till implemented as its core principle combined with other practices have been pointed out in several studies (Peigné et al. 2007, 2015; Cooper et al. 2016; Vincent-Caboud et al. 2017). The use of sectorial climate services (Buontempo et al. 2020; Ceglar et al. 2020) at different spatio-temporal scales will also be a key adaptation measure to reduce the risks and alleviate the impacts of extreme events.

Advanced agricultural technologies may also influence the ability of the region to produce food (Asseng et al. 2019) and adapt to the changing climate and environment. Precision agriculture will make possible a targeted monitoring of plant growth and thus a more efficient use of resources (water, pesticides, nutrients) by combining technologies for data collection (e.g., in-field sensors, weather stations, imaging) with analytical tools, computer vision and artificial intelligence technologies (Bhakta et al. 2019). Precision agriculture has been already applied by some Mediterranean countries (e.g., Israel, Italy, Spain), in viticulture and other crops, and holds a significant technological innovation potential. At the same time, bio and nanotechnologies may help to ensure food security and increase productivity (King et al. 2018; Santeramo et al. 2018a). Cultured, plant-based and insect-based meat are emerging technologies for producing alternatives to meat-

¹⁹ Results from the SWIM-project ACLIMAS, www.aclimas.eu

²⁰ Results from the LIFE-project AGRI-ADAPT, www.agriadapt.eu

²¹ Results from the LIFE-project MEDACC, <http://medacc-life.eu/>

derived proteins whose demand is growing. High costs and consumer reluctance appear to be major obstacles to the implementation of these techniques (Santeramo et al. 2018a; Gómez-Luciano et al. 2019).

3.2.3.2 Mitigation of climate change drivers

Mediterranean climatic conditions host two main crop production systems, rain-fed and irrigated, largely differing in terms of management and, consequently, emissions of N₂O, a potent greenhouse gas. Rain-fed systems are usually characterized by periods with low soil moisture and cold temperatures, thus with decreased soil micro-biological activity and N₂O fluxes. Recent reviews have shown that N₂O emission factors (EF) from rain-fed Mediterranean cropping systems are much lower than the IPCC-default EF threshold of 1% (Aguilera et al. 2013b; Cayuela et al. 2017). Rain-fed crops in Mediterranean regions have lower EFs (EF: 0.27%) than irrigated crops (EF: 0.63%). Irrigated systems usually receive large amounts of water and nitrogen inputs, which create favorable soil conditions for N₂O emissions. Emission factors in these systems fluctuate greatly according to water management and the type and amount of fertilizer used (e.g., synthetic, solid or liquid manures). Sprinkler irrigated crops lead to N₂O emission factor of 0.91%; whereas, drip irrigated systems emit at a lower rate (EF:0.51%) (Cayuela et al. 2017).

Among the most relevant mitigation strategies, there are: nitrogen fertilization optimization; improved water management; better storage of soil organic carbon and carbon sequestration in soil and perennial wood structures of woody crops; management of crop residues and agroindustry by-products.

Nitrogen fertilization optimization

Optimized nitrogen fertilizer application (in terms of input rate and time of application), as well as the careful selection of the type of fertilizer used are crucial to improve crop productivity while reducing N₂O emissions (Sanz-Cobena et al. 2017). An additional effect could be achieved by applying already existing nitrogen (organic fertilizer) when possible or with the use of nitrification and urease inhibitors. Reduction of nitrogen application rates according to soil nitrogen availability and crop yield potential may decrease nitrogen surpluses and subsequent direct and indirect N₂O emissions, while saving energy and abating other greenhouse gas emissions (e.g.,

associated to manufacturing synthetic fertilizers). Significant effects of nitrogen application timing on N₂O emissions have been reported from cereal crops in Mediterranean countries such as Spain (Abalos et al. 2016). The estimated N₂O mitigation potential, through adjusted fertilization (rate and timing) in Mediterranean agro-ecosystems ranges between 30% and 50% compared to non-adjusted practices. Replacing mineral nitrogen with organic fertilization provides not only nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium (NPK) and micronutrients to the soil and crop, but also organic carbon when using solid fertilizers (i.e., solid manure, composts, etc.), which is highly beneficial in Mediterranean soils with low organic carbon contents (Aguilera et al. 2013a; Funes et al. 2019).

In areas where croplands co-exist with livestock farms, using a farm sub-product allows the reuse/recovery of farm products, thus decreasing the volume of waste that needs to be managed, and then avoiding the emission of greenhouse gases both in the management of such wastes and in the manufacturing of new synthetic fertilizers. In Mediterranean areas, the efficient use of manure of fertilizer should be encouraged, and this could be facilitated by increased cooperation between farmers' unions. The use of organic sources of fertilizers may also decrease the need to import synthetic sources thus decreasing greenhouse gas emissions from the production and transport stages. Unfortunately, current intensive livestock production systems are often decoupled from agricultural systems (Sanz-Cobena et al. 2017).

The N₂O emission reduction at plot scale depends on the form of manure used. Solid manures have proved to significantly decrease N₂O emissions (ca. 23%) in Mediterranean systems (Aguilera et al. 2013b), although there is some contradictory information in the scientific literature (Webb et al. 2004; Thorman et al. 2007). For liquid manures (i.e., slurries), no significant differences have been observed when these substitute synthetic nitrogen sources. This seems to be a consequence of the strong similarities between available nitrogen, in the form of NH₄⁺, in both fertilizer types (Meijide et al. 2009; Plaza-Bonilla et al. 2014).

Trade-offs in the form of NH₃ emissions, odors, enhanced denitrification rates due to coexistence of high soil water contents and organic carbon suitable for denitrifiers, must be considered together with the application technology used to fertilize with liquid manures. Nitrification and urease inhibitors (NI) are used in a wide range of agro-climatic regions (Akiyama et al. 2010; Gilsanz

et al. 2016). In Mediterranean soils, NIs have shown high mitigation efficiency in rain-fed and irrigated fields, with a likely indirect effect on denitrification in the latter systems (Meijide et al. 2010). Soil texture may regulate mitigation efficiency (Barth et al. 2008) but to a limited extent, since soil texture has been shown to have a small influence on the inhibition of nitrification (Gilsanz et al. 2016).

Improved water management

The different soil conditions between irrigated and rain-fed crops affect soil microbial processes, which control the fluxes of carbon (carbon dioxide, CO₂; methane, CH₄; organic carbon) and nitrogen (nitrous oxide, N₂O; molecular nitrogen, N₂; nitrate, NO₃; ammonia, NH₃). Soil moisture is a key factor affecting N₂O losses (del Prado et al. 2006; García-Marco et al. 2014), hence the potential for N₂O mitigation linked to irrigation technologies is high, even above 50% (Sánchez-Martín et al. 2008, 2010; Guardia et al. 2016). The lower amounts of water applied in subsurface drip irrigation (SDI) or normal/superficial drip irrigation (DI) through more frequent irrigation events, generate “dry” and “wet” areas in the soil, lowering the overall soil moisture and favoring nitrification over denitrification (Sánchez-Martín et al. 2010), thus reducing N₂O emissions. Drip irrigation systems have shown an N₂O emission factor of only 0.18%, compared to 1% in sprinkler systems (SI), showing the mitigation potential of irrigation technologies in the Mediterranean region (Cayuela et al. 2017). Optimized irrigation techniques to decrease greenhouse gas emissions from Mediterranean regions are particularly used in perennial crops and intensive vegetable cropping systems and in paddy soils (water table management). Other strategies which have been shown to be effective increasing nitrogen use efficiency and reducing N₂O emissions are fertigation and sub-surface drip irrigation (Ayars et al. 2015).

Soil improvement

Most Mediterranean agricultural landscapes are subject to soil organic matter depletion, particularly in the southern and eastern parts of the basin (Ryan et al. 2006). In the northern part of the basin, the issue of low soil organic matter (SOM) is of particular concern for perennial systems such as orchards and vineyards (Meersmans et al. 2012). Maetens et al. (2012) showed that bare soils, vineyards and orchards in Europe are prone to high mean soil losses (10–20 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹), while cropland and fallow show smaller values (6.5 and 5.8 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) largely because the latter occupy

land exhibiting little or no slope. SOM in the Mediterranean countries is somewhat affected by climate change, with land use types such as permanent pasture and cropland being more sensitive than forests (Fantappié et al. 2011). Large losses of SOM may also be caused by erosion caused by the torrential storms that frequently occur in Mediterranean regions (Lagacherie et al. 2018). Likewise, rainfall shortage limits net primary productivity and, in turn, soil carbon buildup. Low carbon inputs driven by limited soil moisture availability are exacerbated by the adoption of certain management practices. Crop residues competition for livestock feeding or the introduction of long fallowing in the crop rotation are two examples of typical management practices in the Mediterranean region that have contributed to the reduction of carbon inputs returned into the soil.

Besides decreases in carbon inputs, agricultural management may also cause soil organic carbon (SOC) losses. Reduction or complete cessation of tillage decreases the direct incorporation of fresh organic debris into deeper soil layers. The absence of tillage (NT) slows down aggregate turnover and increases the physical stabilization of SOC within soil aggregates (Álvaro-Fuentes et al. 2008; Mrabet 2008; Plaza-Bonilla et al. 2010). When tillage is avoided, an approximate annual increase of 1% in SOC can be observed in Mediterranean croplands (Aguilera et al. 2013a). These estimates are highly dependent on soil depth, since vertical SOC distribution in no tillage (NT) and conventional tillage (CT) systems are different (Cantero-Martínez et al. 2007). Further, the assumption of a steady and linear C sequestration may not hold true, because the annual carbon accumulation rate tends to decrease in the long-term (Álvaro-Fuentes et al. 2014).

Long crop rotations have been proposed in rain-fed Mediterranean systems to enhance carbon sequestration and restore soil fertility and structure (Benhabib et al. 2014). The effect of crop rotations on carbon sequestration is highly dependent on time with no significant effect reported in short-term studies (Saber and Mrabet 2002; López-Bellido et al. 2010). Positive effects in long-term experiments (>15 years) could appear if crop biomass is properly managed after harvest (Masri and Ryan 2006; López-Bellido et al. 2010; Martiniello and Teixeira da Silva 2011). The effect of crop rotations on SOC stocks is also dependent on the type of crops included in the rotation (Triberti et al. 2016) and the management of crop residues. The introduction of perennial crops has

shown benefits (di Bene et al. 2011; Pellegrino et al. 2011). The substitution of bare fallows by any crop has been associated with SOC stabilization in NT systems (Álvaro-Fuentes et al. 2009), and to reduced soil erosion (Boellstorff and Benito 2005). The effect of inclusion of grain legumes in rain-fed yearly rotations on carbon sequestration is uncertain, due to their low biomass production, although their conversion to stabilized soil organic matter could be more efficient than that of cereals (Carranca et al. 2009). Consequently, the highest potential of fallow and legumes for mitigating greenhouse gases from these types of cropping systems comes from the avoidance of fertilizer production emissions.

Estimating the greenhouse gas mitigation potential of using crop residues and organic by-products from agroindustry in Mediterranean areas implies accounting for: (i) soil amendments to improve SOM and enhance SOC sequestration (Aguilera et al. 2013a), (ii) feedstock for bioenergy production (di Giacomo and Taglieri 2009; Spinelli and Picchi 2010), (iii) co-substrate for composting (Santos et al. 2016), (iv) feed for livestock (Molina-Alcaide and Yáñez-Ruiz 2008) or (v) construction materials (e.g., animal beds, buildings). The potential to increase SOC levels by using agroindustry by-products, as in crop residues, depends on their composition and degradability. However, agroindustry by-products vary widely in their chemical composition and therefore in their degradation rates. For example, olive and mill waste as they have very low degradation rate in the soil have been found to be good amendments to increase SOC when applied to the soil (Saviozzi et al. 2001).

Besides the potential direct greenhouse gas reduction that any strategy involving the return of the crop residues and agroindustry by-products to the soil may cause (Kassam et al. 2012; Plaza-Bonilla et al. 2014), applying these materials, treated or untreated, as soil amendments can also deliver environmental co-benefits. These benefits include erosion reduction when raw products are used for mulching (Blavet et al. 2009; Jordán et al. 2010) or, in general, the closing the nutrient cycles, with associated potential reductions of fertilizer use and reductions in draught force and fuel consumption for soil tillage (Peltre et al. 2015). Trade-offs may occur with some of the strategies that may result in larger greenhouse gas mitigation potential. For example, the use of crop residues on the soil surface might pose a risk of fire in some Mediterranean areas and, sanitary, pollution and

legal constraints may apply, especially if the by-product is applied to crops e.g., fresh vegetables without pre-treatment.

3.2.3.3 Synergies and trade-offs between adaptation and mitigation

Developing sectorial adaptation strategies requires considering also the mitigation needs and efforts (Sanz-Cobena et al. 2017). For N₂O mitigation and its links with adaptation measures, the pedoclimatic conditions for soil processes in Mediterranean cropping systems imply different N₂O emission patterns as compared to temperate soils (Aguilera et al. 2013b). Nitrification and nitrifier-denitrification, and not denitrification, are very often the main pathways leading to emissions of nitrogen oxides in rain-fed Mediterranean cropping systems (Sánchez-Martín et al. 2008; Kool et al. 2011; Aguilera et al. 2013b; Norton and Ouyang 2019). These two processes are favored by conditions of soil water content (i.e., water filled pore space, WFPS) under saturation (i.e., 40–60% WFPS). Denitrification may play a predominant role in anaerobic soil microsites in intensively managed and irrigated systems (Sanz-Cobena et al. 2012, 2014). Consequently, different cumulative N₂O emissions have been proposed for rainfed crops (0.7 kg N₂O-N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) and for e.g., sprinkler irrigated crops in Mediterranean areas (4.4 kg N₂O-N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) (Cayuela et al. 2017).

The importance and potential for N₂O mitigation and the best mitigation strategy differ greatly depending on the cropping system, being highly affected by adaptation strategies regarding to soil organic carbon and water management in cropping systems. In this sense, increasing the generally low carbon content of Mediterranean soils is an important greenhouse gas mitigation strategy (Robertson et al. 2000), and is also a priority for preventing erosion and improving soil quality. Soil organic carbon content of Mediterranean soils is typically lower than in temperate areas (Chiti et al. 2012), and degradation processes are present in many areas (Lahmar and Ruellan 2007), a trend that is expected to be exacerbated by climate change in the coming decades (Al-Adamat et al. 2007). However, SOC in Mediterranean croplands is also highly responsive to management changes such as organic amendments, cover crops and tillage reductions, and there is a high potential for SOC storage through land restoration. Significant carbon sequestration rates have been observed after the application of recommended management practices and organic management

in Mediterranean cropping systems (Aguilera et al. 2013a). This high responsiveness is reflected in SOC storage rates nearly one order of magnitude higher than the 0.4% annual SOC increase proposed by the “4 per 1,000” initiative, as reported in a recent meta-analysis (Chabbi et al. 2017; Minasny et al. 2017). This meta-analysis underlined the differences between herbaceous and woody crops regarding the carbon sequestration potential and

the practices to be applied in each system. Thus, organic fertilizers, tillage reduction and residue retention are effective practices in herbaceous systems. Woody systems, in which the storage potential is higher, would greatly benefit from maintaining a soil cover and making use of agro-industry byproducts, such as composted olive mill waste, as a source of organic matter (Vicente-Vicente et al. 2016).

References

- Abalos D, Jeffery S, Drury CF, Wagner-Riddle C 2016 Improving fertilizer management in the U.S. and Canada for N₂O mitigation: Understanding potential positive and negative side-effects on corn yields. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 221, 214–221. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2016.01.044](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.01.044)
- Abd-Elmabod SK, Fitch AC, Zhang Z, Ali RR, Jones L 2019 Rapid urbanisation threatens fertile agricultural land and soil carbon in the Nile delta. *J. Environ. Manage.* 252, 109668. doi: [10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109668](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109668)
- Aguilera E, Lassaletta L, Gattinger A, Gimeno BS 2013a Managing soil carbon for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Mediterranean cropping systems: A meta-analysis. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 168, 25–36. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2013.02.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.02.003)
- Aguilera E, Lassaletta L, Sanz-Cobena A, Garnier J, Vallejo A 2013b The potential of organic fertilizers and water management to reduce N₂O emissions in Mediterranean climate cropping systems. A review. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 164, 32–52. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2012.09.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2012.09.006)
- Akiyama H, Yan X, Yagi K 2010 Evaluation of effectiveness of enhanced-efficiency fertilizers as mitigation options for N₂O and NO emissions from agricultural soils: meta-analysis. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 16, 1837–1846. doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.02031.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.02031.x)
- Al-Adamat R, Rawajfih Z, Easter M, Paustian K, Coleman K et al. 2007 Predicted soil organic carbon stocks and changes in Jordan between 2000 and 2030 made using the GEFSOC Modelling System. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 122, 35–45. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2007.01.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2007.01.006)
- Al-Bakri J, Suleiman A, Abdulla F, Ayad J 2011 Potential impact of climate change on rainfed agriculture of a semi-arid basin in Jordan. *Phys. Chem. Earth* 36, 125–134. doi: [10.1016/j.pce.2010.06.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2010.06.001)
- Álvaro-Fuentes J, Cantero-Martínez C, López M V., Paustian K, Denef K et al. 2009 Soil aggregation and soil organic carbon stabilization: effects of management in semiarid Mediterranean agroecosystems. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 73, 1519–1529. doi: [10.2136/sssaj2008.0333](https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2008.0333)
- Álvaro-Fuentes J, López M V., Cantero-Martínez C, Arrúe JL 2008 Tillage effects on soil organic carbon fractions in Mediterranean dryland agroecosystems. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 72, 541. doi: [10.2136/sssaj2007.0164](https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2007.0164)
- Álvaro-Fuentes J, Plaza-Bonilla D, Arrúe JL, Lampurlanés J, Cantero-Martínez C 2014 Soil organic carbon storage in a no-tillage chronosequence under Mediterranean conditions. *Plant Soil* 376, 31–41. doi: [10.1007/s11104-012-1167-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-012-1167-x)
- Annabi M, Bahri H, M'hamed HC 2018 Integrating future climate change, CO₂ increase and technology progress on wheat production in Northern Tunisia, in *Recent Advances in Environmental Science from the Euro-Mediterranean and Surrounding Regions. Proceedings of Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (EMCEI-1), Tunisia 2017*, eds. Kallel A, Ksibi M, Ben Dhia H, Khélifi N (Springer International Publishing), 69–70. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-70548-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-70548-4)
- Arnaez J, Lasanta T, Errea MP, Ortigosa L 2011 Land abandonment, landscape evolution, and soil erosion in a Spanish Mediterranean mountain region: The case of Camero Viejo. *L. Degrad. Dev.* 22, 537–550. doi: [10.1002/ldr.1032](https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.1032)
- Asseng S, Martre P, Maiorano A, Rötter RP, O'Leary GJ et al. 2019 Climate change impact and adaptation for wheat protein. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 25, 155–173. doi: [10.1111/gcb.14481](https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14481)
- Ayars JE, Fulton A, Taylor B 2015 Subsurface drip irrigation in California—Here to stay? *Agric. Water Manag.* 157, 39–47. doi: [10.1016/j.agwat.2015.01.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2015.01.001)
- Bajocco S, de Angelis A, Perini L, Ferrara A, Salvati L 2012 The impact of Land Use/Land Cover Changes on land degradation dynamics: A Mediterranean case study. *Environ. Manage.* 49, 980–989. doi: [10.1007/s00267-012-9831-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-012-9831-8)
- Barth G, Von Tucher S, Schmidhalter U 2008 Effectiveness of 3,4-Dimethylpyrazole Phosphate as Nitrification Inhibitor in Soil as Influenced by Inhibitor Concentration, Application Form, and Soil Matric Potential. *Pedosphere* 18, 378–385. doi: [10.1016/s1002-0160\(08\)60028-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1002-0160(08)60028-4)
- Barton CM, Ullah IIT, Bergin SM 2010 Land use, water and Mediterranean landscapes: Modelling long-term dynamics of complex socio-ecological systems. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 368, 5275–5297. doi: [10.1098/rsta.2010.0193](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2010.0193)
- Barton CM, Ullah IIT, Bergin SM, Sarjoughian HS, Mayer GR et al. 2016 Experimental socioecology: Integrative science for anthropocene landscape dynamics. *Anthropocene* 13, 34–45. doi: [10.1016/j.ancene.2015.12.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ancene.2015.12.004)
- Basso L, Hendriks IE, Duarte CM 2015 Juvenile pen shells (*Pinna nobilis*) tolerate acidification but are vulnerable to warming. *Estuaries and Coasts* 38, 1976–1985. doi: [10.1007/s12237-015-9948-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-015-9948-0)
- Bebber DP, Holmes T, Gurr SJ 2014 The global spread of crop pests and pathogens. *Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.* 23, 1398–1407. doi: [10.1111/geb.12214](https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12214)
- Bebber DP, Ramotowski MAT, Gurr SJ 2013 Crop pests and pathogens move polewards in a warming world. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 3, 985–988. doi: [10.1038/nclimate1990](https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1990)
- Behrenfeld MJ, O'Malley RT, Siegel DA, McClain CR, Sarmiento JL et al. 2006 Climate-driven trends in contemporary ocean productivity. *Nature* 444,

- 752–755. doi: [10.1038/nature05317](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature05317)
- Benhabib O, Yazar A, Qadir M, Lourenço E, Jacobsen S-E 2014 How Can We Improve Mediterranean Cropping Systems? *J. Agron. Crop Sci.* 200, 325–332. doi: [10.1111/jac.12066](https://doi.org/10.1111/jac.12066)
- Berge JA, Bjerkeng B, Pettersen O, Schaanning MT, Øxnevad S 2006 Effects of increased sea water concentrations of CO₂ on growth of the bivalve *Mytilus edulis* L. *Chemosphere* 62, 681–687. doi: [10.1016/j.chemosphere.2005.04.111](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2005.04.111)
- Bernabucci U, Basiricò L, Morera P, Dipasquale D, Vitali A et al. 2015 Effect of summer season on milk protein fractions in Holstein cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98, 1815–1827. doi: [10.3168/jds.2014-8788](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-8788)
- Bernabucci U, Lacetera N, Baumgard LH, Rhoads RP, Ronchi B et al. 2010 Metabolic and hormonal acclimation to heat stress in domesticated ruminants. *Animal* 4, 1167–1183. doi: [10.1017/S175173111000090X](https://doi.org/10.1017/S175173111000090X)
- Bhakta I, Phadikar S, Majumder K 2019 State-of-the-art technologies in precision agriculture: a systematic review. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 99, 4878–4888. doi: [10.1002/jsfa.9693](https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.9693)
- Bird DN, Benabdallah S, Gouda N, Hummel F, Koebel J et al. 2016 Modelling climate change impacts on and adaptation strategies for agriculture in Sardinia and Tunisia using AquaCrop and value-at-risk. *Sci. Total Environ.* 543, 1019–1027. doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.07.035](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.07.035)
- Blauhut V, Gudmundsson L, Stahl K 2015 Towards pan-European drought risk maps: quantifying the link between drought indices and reported drought impacts. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 10, 14008. doi: [10.1088/1748-9326/10/1/014008](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/1/014008)
- Blavet D, de Noni G, le Bissonnais Y, Leonard M, Maillo L et al. 2009 Effect of land use and management on the early stages of soil water erosion in French Mediterranean vineyards. *Soil Tillage Res.* 106, 124–136. doi: [10.1016/j.still.2009.04.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2009.04.010)
- Boellstorff D, Benito G 2005 Impacts of set-aside policy on the risk of soil erosion in central Spain. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 107, 231–243. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2004.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2004.11.002)
- Bonaccio M, di Castelnuovo A, Bonanni A, Costanzo S, de Lucia F et al. 2014 Decline of the Mediterranean diet at a time of economic crisis. Results from the Moli-sani study. *Nutr. Metab. Cardiovasc. Dis.* 24, 853–860. doi: [10.1016/j.numecd.2014.02.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.numecd.2014.02.014)
- Bonaccio M, Iacoviello L, de Gaetano G 2012 The Mediterranean diet: The reasons for a success. *Thromb. Res.* 129, 401–404. doi: [10.1016/j.thromres.2011.10.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2011.10.018)
- Bowman DMJS, Williamson GJ, Abatzoglou JT, Kolden CA, Cochrane MA et al. 2017 Human exposure and sensitivity to globally extreme wildfire events. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 1, 1–6. doi: [10.1038/s41559-016-0058](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-016-0058)
- Buontempo C, Hutjes R, Beavis P, Berckmans J, Cagnazzo C et al. 2020 Fostering the development of climate services through Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) for agriculture applications. *Weather Clim. Extrem.* 27, 100226. doi: [10.1016/j.wace.2019.100226](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2019.100226)
- Bureau JC, Swinnen J 2018 EU policies and global food security. *Glob. Food Sec.* 16, 106–115. doi: [10.1016/j.gfs.2017.12.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2017.12.001)
- Burge CA, Eakin CM, Friedman CS, Froelich B, Hershberger PK et al. 2014 Climate change influences on marine infectious diseases: implications for management and society. *Ann. Rev. Mar. Sci.* 6, 249–277. doi: [10.1146/annurev-marine-010213-135029](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-010213-135029)
- Cantero-Martínez C, Angás P, Lampurlanés J 2007 Long-term yield and water use efficiency under various tillage systems in Mediterranean rainfed conditions. *Ann. Appl. Biol.* 150, 293–305. doi: [10.1111/j.1744-7348.2007.00142.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7348.2007.00142.x)
- Capone R, El Bilali H, Elferchichi A, Lamaddalena N, Lamberti L 2012 Natural resources and food in the Mediterranean, in *MediTERRA 2012: The mediterranean diet for sustainable regional development*, ed. CIHEAM (Paris: Presses de Sciences Po), 171–193.
- Caracciolo F, Gotor E, Santeramo FG 2014 European Common Agricultural Policy Impacts On Developing Countries Commodities Prices. *Reg. Sect. Econ. Stud.* 14, 2.
- Caracciolo F, Santeramo FG 2013 Price Trends and Income Inequalities: Will Sub-Saharan Africa Reduce the Gap? *African Dev. Rev.* 25, 42–54. doi: [10.1111/j.1467-8268.2013.12012.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8268.2013.12012.x)
- Carranca C, Oliveira A, Pampulha E, Torres MO 2009 Temporal dynamics of soil nitrogen, carbon and microbial activity in conservative and disturbed fields amended with mature white lupine and oat residues. *Geoderma* 151, 50–59. doi: [10.1016/j.geoderma.2009.03.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2009.03.012)
- Carranza-Gallego G, Guzmán GI, García-Ruiz R, González de Molina M, Aguilera E 2018 Contribution of old wheat varieties to climate change mitigation under contrasting managements and rainfed Mediterranean conditions. *J. Clean. Prod.* 195, 111–121. doi: [10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.188](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.188)
- Cayuela ML, Aguilera E, Sanz-Cobena A, Adams DC, Abalos D et al. 2017 Direct nitrous oxide emissions in Mediterranean climate cropping systems: Emission factors based on a meta-analysis of available measurement data. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 238, 25–35. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2016.10.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.10.006)
- Ceglar A, Toreti A, Zampieri M, Manstretta V, Bettati T et al. 2020 Clisagri: An R package for agro-climate services. *Clim. Serv.* 20, 100197. doi: [10.1016/j.cliser.2020.100197](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2020.100197)
- Ceglar A, Zampieri M, Toreti A, Dentener FJ 2019 Observed Northward Migration of Agro-Climatic Zones in Europe Will Further Accelerate Under Climate Change. *Earth's Futur.* 7, 1088–1101. doi: [10.1029/2019ef001178](https://doi.org/10.1029/2019ef001178)

- Chabbi A, Lehmann J, Ciais P, Loescher HW, Cotrufo MF et al. 2017 Aligning agriculture and climate policy. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 7, 307–309. doi: [10.1038/nclimate3286](https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3286)
- Chatterjee N, Nair PKR, Chakraborty S, Nair VD 2018 Changes in soil carbon stocks across the Forest-Agroforest-Agriculture/Pasture continuum in various agroecological regions: A meta-analysis. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 266, 55–67. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2018.07.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.07.014)
- Chatzopoulos T, Pérez Domínguez I, Zampieri M, Toreti A 2019 Climate extremes and agricultural commodity markets: A global economic analysis of regionally simulated events. *Weather Clim. Extrem.*, 100193. doi: [10.1016/j.wace.2019.100193](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2019.100193)
- Chen C-C, McCarl B, Chang C-C 2012 Climate change, sea level rise and rice: Global market implications. *Clim. Change* 110, 543–560. doi: [10.1007/s10584-011-0074-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0074-0)
- Cheung WWL, Frölicher TL, Asch RG, Jones MC, Pinsky ML et al. 2016 Building confidence in projections of the responses of living marine resources to climate change. *ICES J. Mar. Sci. J. du Cons.* 73, 1283–1296. doi: [10.1093/icesjms/fsv250](https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsv250)
- Chiti T, Gardin L, Perugini L, Quarantino R, Vaccari FP et al. 2012 Soil organic carbon stock assessment for the different cropland land uses in Italy. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 48, 9–17. doi: [10.1007/s00374-011-0599-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-011-0599-4)
- Chourghal N, Lhomme JP, Huard F, Aidaoui A 2016 Climate change in Algeria and its impact on durum wheat. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 16, 1623–1634. doi: [10.1007/s10113-015-0889-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0889-8)
- CIHEAM, FAO 2015 Mediterranean food consumption patterns: diet, environment, society, economy and health. A White Paper.
- Cioffi A, Dell'Aquila C 2004 The effects of trade policies for fresh fruit and vegetables of the European Union. *Food Policy* 29, 169–185. doi: [10.1016/s0306-9192\(04\)00010-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-9192(04)00010-7)
- Cioffi A, Santeramo FG, Vitale CD 2011 The price stabilization effects of the EU entry price scheme for fruit and vegetables. *Agric. Econ.* 42, 405–418. doi: [10.1111/j.1574-0862.2010.00526.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-0862.2010.00526.x)
- Cooper J, Baranski M, Stewart G, Nobel-de Lange M, Bàrberi P et al. 2016 Shallow non-inversion tillage in organic farming maintains crop yields and increases soil C stocks: a meta-analysis. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 36, 22. doi: [10.1007/s13593-016-0354-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-016-0354-1)
- de Rensis F, García-Ispierto I, López-Gatius F 2015 Seasonal heat stress: Clinical implications and hormone treatments for the fertility of dairy cows. *Theriogenology* 84, 659–666. doi: [10.1016/j.theriogenology.2015.04.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2015.04.021)
- Debolini M, Valette E, François M, Chéry JP 2015 Mapping land use competition in the rural-urban fringe and future perspectives on land policies: A case study of Meknès (Morocco). *Land use policy* 47, 373–381. doi: [10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.01.035](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.01.035)
- del Pozo A, Brunel-Saldias N, Engler A, Ortega-Farías S, Acevedo-Opazo C et al. 2019 Climate change impacts and adaptation strategies of agriculture in Mediterranean-climate regions (MCRs). *Sustain.* 11, 2769. doi: [10.3390/su11102769](https://doi.org/10.3390/su11102769)
- del Pozo A, Yáñez A, Matus IA, Tapia G, Castillo D et al. 2016 Physiological Traits Associated with Wheat Yield Potential and Performance under Water-Stress in a Mediterranean Environment. *Front. Plant Sci.* 7, 987. doi: [10.3389/fpls.2016.00987](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.00987)
- del Prado A, Merino P, Estavillo JM, Pinto M, González-Murua C 2006 N₂O and NO emissions from different N sources and under a range of soil water contents. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosystems* 74, 229–243. doi: [10.1007/s10705-006-9001-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-006-9001-6)
- di Bene C, Tavarini S, Mazzoncini M, Angelini LG 2011 Changes in soil chemical parameters and organic matter balance after 13 years of ramie [*Boehmeria nivea* (L.) Gaud.] cultivation in the Mediterranean region. *Eur. J. Agron.* 35, 154–163. doi: [10.1016/j.eja.2011.05.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2011.05.007)
- di Giacomo G, Taglieri L 2009 Renewable energy benefits with conversion of woody residues to pellets. *Energy* 34, 724–731. doi: [10.1016/j.energy.2008.08.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2008.08.010)
- Díez-Palet I, Funes I, Savé R, Biel C, de Herralde F et al. 2019 Blooming under Mediterranean Climate: Estimating Cultivar-Specific Chill and Heat Requirements of Almond and Apple Trees Using a Statistical Approach. *Agronomy* 9, 760. doi: [10.3390/agronomy9110760](https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy9110760)
- Doney SC, Fabry VJ, Feely RA, Kleypas JA 2009 Ocean acidification: The other CO₂ problem. *Ann. Rev. Mar. Sci.* 1, 169–192. doi: [10.1146/annurev.marine.010908.163834](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.marine.010908.163834)
- Drine I 2011 Climate Change Compounding Risks in North Africa.
- EEA 2019 Climate change adaptation in the agriculture sector in Europe.
- Fader M, Shi S, Von Bloh W, Bondeau A, Cramer W 2016 Mediterranean irrigation under climate change: More efficient irrigation needed to compensate for increases in irrigation water requirements. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 20, 953–973. doi: [10.5194/hess-20-953-2016](https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-20-953-2016)
- Falcucci A, Maiorano L, Boitani L 2007 Changes in land-use/land-cover patterns in Italy and their implications for biodiversity conservation. *Landsc. Ecol.* 22, 617–631. doi: [10.1007/s10980-006-9056-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-006-9056-4)
- Fantappiè M, L'Abate G, Costantini EAC 2011 The influence of climate change on the soil organic carbon content in Italy from 1961 to 2008. *Geomorphology* 135, 343–352. doi: [10.1016/j.geomorph.2011.02.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2011.02.006)
- FAO 2017 FAOSTAT.
- FAO 2018 The State of Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries. Rome.

- Feyen L, Ciscar JC, Gosling S, Ibarreta D, Soria A 2020 Climate change impacts and adaptation in Europe. JRC PESETA IV final report. Luxembourg. doi: [10.2760/171121](https://doi.org/10.2760/171121)
- Flecha S, Pérez FF, García-Lafuente J, Sammartino S, Ríos AF et al. 2015 Trends of pH decrease in the Mediterranean Sea through high frequency observational data: indication of ocean acidification in the basin. *Sci. Rep.* 5, 16770. doi: [10.1038/srep16770](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep16770)
- Fontana G, Toreti A, Ceglar A, de Sanctis G 2015 Early heat waves over Italy and their impacts on durum wheat yields. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 15, 1631–1637. doi: [10.5194/nhess-15-1631-2015](https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-15-1631-2015)
- Funes I, Aranda X, Biel C, Carbó J, Camps F et al. 2016 Future climate change impacts on apple flowering date in a Mediterranean subbasin. *Agric. Water Manag.* 164, 19–27. doi: [10.1016/j.agwat.2015.06.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2015.06.013)
- Funes I, Savé R, Rovira P, Molowny-Horas R, Alcañiz JM et al. 2019 Agricultural soil organic carbon stocks in the north-eastern Iberian Peninsula: Drivers and spatial variability. *Sci. Total Environ.* 668, 283–294. doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.02.317](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.02.317)
- Galli A, Halle M, Grunewald N 2015 Physical limits to resource access and utilisation and their economic implications in Mediterranean economies. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 51, 125–136. doi: [10.1016/j.envsci.2015.04.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.04.002)
- Galli A, Iha K, Halle M, El Bilali H, Grunewald N et al. 2017 Mediterranean countries' food consumption and sourcing patterns: An Ecological Footprint viewpoint. *Sci. Total Environ.* 578, 383–391. doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.191](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.191)
- Gantner V, Bobic T, Gantner R, Gregic M, Kuterovac K et al. 2017 Differences in response to heat stress due to production level and breed of dairy cows. *Int. J. Biometeorol.* 61, 1675–1685. doi: [10.1007/s00484-017-1348-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-017-1348-7)
- García-Marco S, Ravella SR, Chadwick DR, Vallejo A, Gregory AS et al. 2014 Ranking factors affecting emissions of GHG from incubated agricultural soils. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 65, 573–583. doi: [10.1111/ejss.12143](https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12143)
- García Martínez M, Poole N 2004 The development of private fresh produce safety standards: Implications for developing Mediterranean exporting countries. *Food Policy* 29, 229–255. doi: [10.1016/j.foodpol.2004.04.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2004.04.002)
- Gazeau F, Alliouane S, Bock C, Bramanti L, López Correa M et al. 2014 Impact of ocean acidification and warming on the Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*). *Front. Mar. Sci.* 1, 62. doi: [10.3389/fmars.2014.00062](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2014.00062)
- Genua-Olmedo A, Alcaraz C, Caiola N, Ibáñez C 2016 Sea level rise impacts on rice production: The Ebro Delta as an example. *Sci. Total Environ.* 571, 1200–1210. doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.07.136](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.07.136)
- Gilsanz C, Báez D, Misselbrook TH, Dhanoa MS, Cárdenas LM 2016 Development of emission factors and efficiency of two nitrification inhibitors, DCD and DMPP. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 216, 1–8. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2015.09.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2015.09.030)
- Girard C, Pulido-Velazquez M, Rinaudo J-D, Pagé C, Caballero Y 2015 Integrating top-down and bottom-up approaches to design global change adaptation at the river basin scale. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 34, 132–146. doi: [10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.07.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.07.002)
- Gómez-Luciano CA, de Aguiar LK, Vriesekoop F, Urbano B 2019 Consumers' willingness to purchase three alternatives to meat proteins in the United Kingdom, Spain, Brazil and the Dominican Republic. *Food Qual. Prefer.* 78, 103732. doi: [10.1016/j.foodqual.2019.103732](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2019.103732)
- Grasso M, Feola G 2012 Mediterranean agriculture under climate change: Adaptive capacity, adaptation, and ethics. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 12, 607–618. doi: [10.1007/s10113-011-0274-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-011-0274-1)
- Guardia G, Tellez-Rio A, García-Marco S, Martin-Lammerding D, Tenorio JL et al. 2016 Effect of tillage and crop (cereal versus legume) on greenhouse gas emissions and Global Warming Potential in a non-irrigated Mediterranean field. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 221, 187–197. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2016.01.047](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.01.047)
- Harmanny KS, Malek Ž 2019 Adaptations in irrigated agriculture in the Mediterranean region: an overview and spatial analysis of implemented strategies. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 19, 1401–1416. doi: [10.1007/s10113-019-01494-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-019-01494-8)
- Hatfield JL, Dold C 2019 Water-use efficiency: Advances and challenges in a changing climate. *Front. Plant Sci.* 10, 103. doi: [10.3389/fpls.2019.00103](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.00103)
- Havenhand JN, Buttler F-R, Thorndyke MC, Williamson JE 2008 Near-future levels of ocean acidification reduce fertilization success in a sea urchin. *Curr. Biol.* 18, R651–R652. doi: [10.1016/j.cub.2008.06.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2008.06.015)
- Hendriks IE, Duarte CM, Álvarez M 2010 Vulnerability of marine biodiversity to ocean acidification: A meta-analysis. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 86, 157–164. doi: [10.1016/j.ecss.2009.11.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2009.11.022)
- Hoegh-Guldberg O, Mumby PJ, Hooten AJ, Steneck RS, Greenfield P et al. 2007 Coral reefs under rapid climate change and ocean acidification. *Science (80-. J.)* 318, 1737–1742. doi: [10.1126/science.1152509](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1152509)
- Iglesias A, Garrote L 2015 Adaptation strategies for agricultural water management under climate change in Europe. *Agric. Water Manag.* 155, 113–124. doi: [10.1016/j.agwat.2015.03.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2015.03.014)
- Jordán A, Zavala LM, Gil J 2010 Effects of mulching on soil physical properties and runoff under semi-arid conditions in southern Spain. *Catena* 81, 77–85. doi: [10.1016/j.catena.2010.01.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2010.01.007)
- Karamesouti M, Detsis V, Kounalaki A, Vasiliou P,

- Salvati L et al. 2015 Land-use and land degradation processes affecting soil resources: Evidence from a traditional Mediterranean cropland (Greece). *Catena* 132, 45–55. doi: [10.1016/j.catena.2015.04.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2015.04.010)
- Kassam A, Friedrich T, Derpsch R, Lahmar R, Mrabet R et al. 2012 Conservation agriculture in the dry Mediterranean climate. *F. Crop. Res.* 132, 7–17. doi: [10.1016/j.fcr.2012.02.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2012.02.023)
- Kauppi PE, Ausubel JH, Fang J, Mather AS, Sedjo RA et al. 2006 Returning forests analyzed with the forest identity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 103, 17574–17579. doi: [10.1073/pnas.0608343103](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0608343103)
- Kimball BA 2016 Crop responses to elevated CO₂ and interactions with H₂O, N, and temperature. *Curr. Opin. Plant Biol.* 31, 36–43. doi: [10.1016/j.pbi.2016.03.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pbi.2016.03.006)
- King T, Osmond-McLeod MJ, Duffy LL 2018 Nanotechnology in the food sector and potential applications for the poultry industry. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 72, 62–73. doi: [10.1016/j.tifs.2017.11.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2017.11.015)
- Kool DM, Dolfing J, Wrage N, Van Groenigen JW 2011 Nitrifier denitrification as a distinct and significant source of nitrous oxide from soil. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 43, 174–178. doi: [10.1016/j.soilbio.2010.09.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2010.09.030)
- Kurihara H 2008 Effects of CO₂-driven ocean acidification on the early developmental stages of invertebrates. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 373, 275–284. doi: [10.3354/meps07802](https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07802)
- Kurihara H, Kato S, Ishimatsu A 2007 Effects of increased seawater pCO₂ on early development of the oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. *Aquat. Biol.* 1, 91–98. doi: [10.3354/ab00009](https://doi.org/10.3354/ab00009)
- Lagacherie P, Álvaro-Fuentes J, Annabi M, Bernoux M, Bouarfa S et al. 2018 Managing Mediterranean soil resources under global change: expected trends and mitigation strategies. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 18, 663–675. doi: [10.1007/s10113-017-1239-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-017-1239-9)
- Lahmar R, Ruellan A 2007 Soil degradation in the Mediterranean region and cooperative strategies. *Cah. Agric.* 16, 318–323. doi: [10.1684/agr.2007.0119](https://doi.org/10.1684/agr.2007.0119)
- Larson BA, Nicolaidis E, Al Zu'bi B, Sukkar N, Laraki K et al. 2002 The Impact of Environmental Regulations on Exports: Case Study Results from Cyprus, Jordan, Morocco, Syria, Tunisia, and Turkey. *World Dev.* 30, 1057–1072. doi: [10.1016/s0305-750x\(02\)00023-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0305-750x(02)00023-2)
- Lassaletta L, Billen G, Grizzetti B, Garnier J, Leach AM et al. 2014 Food and feed trade as a driver in the global nitrogen cycle: 50-year trends. *Biogeochemistry* 118, 225–241. doi: [10.1007/s10533-013-9923-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-013-9923-4)
- Lassaletta L, Romero E, Billen G, Garnier J, García-Gómez H et al. 2012 Spatialized N budgets in a large agricultural Mediterranean watershed: High loading and low transfer. *Biogeosciences* 9, 57–70. doi: [10.5194/bg-9-57-2012](https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-9-57-2012)
- Lesk C, Rowhani P, Ramankutty N 2016 Influence of extreme weather disasters on global crop production. *Nature* 529, 84–87. doi: [10.1038/nature16467](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16467)
- Liebig MA, Franzluebbers AJ, Alvarez C, Chiesa TD, Lewczuk N et al. 2016 MAGNet: An international network to foster mitigation of agricultural greenhouse gases. *Carbon Manag.* 7, 243–248. doi: [10.1080/17583004.2016.1180586](https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2016.1180586)
- Lin BB 2011 Resilience in Agriculture through Crop Diversification: Adaptive Management for Environmental Change. *Bioscience* 61, 183–193. doi: [10.1525/bio.2011.61.3.4](https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2011.61.3.4)
- López-Bellido RJ, Fontán JM, López-Bellido FJ, López-Bellido L 2010 Carbon Sequestration by Tillage, Rotation, and Nitrogen Fertilization in a Mediterranean Vertisol. *Agron. J.* 102, 310. doi: [10.2134/agronj2009.0165](https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj2009.0165)
- Maetens W, Vanmaercke M, Poesen J, Jankauskas B, Jankauskiene G et al. 2012 Effects of land use on annual runoff and soil loss in Europe and the Mediterranean. *Prog. Phys. Geogr. Earth Environ.* 36, 599–653. doi: [10.1177/0309133312451303](https://doi.org/10.1177/0309133312451303)
- Malek Ž, Verburg PH, Geijzendorffer IR, Bondeau A, Cramer W 2018 Global change effects on land management in the Mediterranean region. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 50, 238–254. doi: [10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.04.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.04.007)
- Marquez-Ramos L, Martinez-Gomez VD 2016 On the effect of EU trade preferences: evidence for monthly exports of fruit and vegetables from Morocco. *New Medit* 15, 14–21.
- Martiniello P, Teixeira da Silva JA 2011 Physiological and Bioagronomical Aspects Involved in Growth and Yield Components of Cultivated Forage Species in Mediterranean Environments: A Review. *Eur. J. Plant Sci. Biotechnol.* 5, 64–98.
- Masri Z, Ryan J 2006 Soil organic matter and related physical properties in a Mediterranean wheat-based rotation trial. *Soil Tillage Res.* 87, 146–154. doi: [10.1016/j.still.2005.03.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2005.03.003)
- Mavromatis T 2015 Crop-climate relationships of cereals in Greece and the impacts of recent climate trends. *Theor. Appl. Climatol.* 120, 417–432. doi: [10.1007/s00704-014-1179-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-014-1179-y)
- McCarl BA, Musumba M, Smith JB, Kirshen P, Jones R et al. 2015 Climate change vulnerability and adaptation strategies in Egypt's agricultural sector. *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Chang.* 20, 1097–1109. doi: [10.1007/s11027-013-9520-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-013-9520-9)
- Medina A, Akbar A, Baazeem A, Rodriguez A, Magan N 2017 Climate change, food security and mycotoxins: Do we know enough? *Fungal Biol. Rev.* 31, 143–154. doi: [10.1016/j.fbr.2017.04.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbr.2017.04.002)
- Meersmans J, Martin MP, Lacarce E, de Baets S, Jolivet C et al. 2012 A high resolution map of French soil organic carbon. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 32, 841–851.

- doi: [10.1007/s13593-012-0086-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-012-0086-9)
- Meijide A, Cárdenas LM, Sánchez-Martín L, Vallejo A 2010 Carbon dioxide and methane fluxes from a barley field amended with organic fertilizers under Mediterranean climatic conditions. *Plant Soil* 328, 353–367. doi: [10.1007/s11104-009-0114-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-009-0114-y)
- Meijide A, García-Torres L, Arce A, Vallejo A 2009 Nitrogen oxide emissions affected by organic fertilization in a non-irrigated Mediterranean barley field. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 132, 106–115. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2009.03.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2009.03.005)
- Minasny B, Malone BP, McBratney AB, Angers DA, Arrouays D et al. 2017 Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma* 292, 59–86. doi: [10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.01.002)
- Molina-Alcaide E, Yáñez-Ruiz DR 2008 Potential use of olive by-products in ruminant feeding: A review. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 147, 247–264. doi: [10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2007.09.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2007.09.021)
- Moritz MA, Battlori E, Bradstock RA, Gill AM, Handmer J et al. 2014 Learning to coexist with wildfire. *Nature* 515, 58–66. doi: [10.1038/nature13946](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13946)
- Mougou R, Mansour M, Iglesias A, Chebbi RZ, Battagliani A 2011 Climate change and agricultural vulnerability: A case study of rain-fed wheat in Kairouan, Central Tunisia. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 11, 137–142. doi: [10.1007/s10113-010-0179-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-010-0179-4)
- Mrabet R 2008 *No-Tillage systems for sustainable dryland agriculture in Morocco*. INRA Publication, Fanigraph Edition.
- Mueller ND, Gerber JS, Johnston M, Ray DK, Ramankutty N et al. 2012 Closing yield gaps through nutrient and water management. *Nature* 490, 254–257. doi: [10.1038/nature11420](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11420)
- Niedertscheider M, Erb K 2014 Land system change in Italy from 1884 to 2007: Analysing the North-South divergence on the basis of an integrated indicator framework. *Land use policy* 39, 366–375. doi: [10.1016/j.landusepol.2014.01.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2014.01.015)
- Norton J, Ouyang Y 2019 Controls and adaptive management of nitrification in agricultural soils. *Front. Microbiol.* 10. doi: [10.3389/fmicb.2019.01931](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.01931)
- Padilla FM, Vidal B, Sánchez J, Pugnaire FI 2010 Land-use changes and carbon sequestration through the twentieth century in a Mediterranean mountain ecosystem: implications for land management. *J. Environ. Manage.* 91, 2688–2695. doi: [10.1016/j.jenvman.2010.07.031](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2010.07.031)
- Pala M, Oweis T, Benli B, de Pauw E, El Mourid M et al. 2011 Assessment of wheat yield gap in the Mediterranean: case studies from Morocco, Syria and Turkey. *ICARDA Rep.*, 36.
- Parker LM, Ross PM, O'Connor WA 2009 The effect of ocean acidification and temperature on the fertilization and embryonic development of the Sydney rock oyster *Saccostrea glomerata* (Gould 1850). *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 15, 2123–2136. doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01895.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01895.x)
- Parker LM, Ross PM, O'Connor WA 2010 Comparing the effect of elevated pCO₂ and temperature on the fertilization and early development of two species of oysters. *Mar. Biol.* 157, 2435–2452. doi: [10.1007/s00227-010-1508-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-010-1508-3)
- Pauly D, Zeller D 2016 Catch reconstructions reveal that global marine fisheries catches are higher than reported and declining. *Nat. Commun.* 7, 10244. doi: [10.1038/ncomms10244](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10244)
- Peigné J, Ball BC, Roger-Estrade J, David C 2007 Is conservation tillage suitable for organic farming? A review. *Soil Use Manag.* 23, 129–144. doi: [10.1111/j.1475-2743.2006.00082.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.2006.00082.x)
- Peigné J, Lefevre V, Vian JF, Fleury P 2015 Conservation agriculture in organic farming: experiences, challenges and opportunities in Europe, in *Conservation Agriculture* (Switzerland: Springer International Publishing), 559–578. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-11620-4_21](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11620-4_21)
- Pellegrino E, di Bene C, Tozzini C, Bonari E 2011 Impact on soil quality of a 10-year-old short-rotation coppice poplar stand compared with intensive agricultural and uncultivated systems in a Mediterranean area. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 140, 245–254. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2010.12.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2010.12.011)
- Peltre C, Nyord T, Bruun S, Jensen LS, Magid J 2015 Repeated soil application of organic waste amendments reduces draught force and fuel consumption for soil tillage. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 211, 94–101. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2015.06.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2015.06.004)
- Petit M, Le Grusse P 2018 Food and water security in the Mediterranean Basin, in *The Oxford handbook of food, water and society*, eds. Allan T, Bromwich B, Keulertz M, Colman A (Oxford, Royaume-Uni: Oxford University Press), 1–16.
- Phogat V, Pitt T, Cox JW, Šimůnek J, Skewes MA 2018 Soil water and salinity dynamics under sprinkler irrigated almond exposed to a varied salinity stress at different growth stages. *Agric. Water Manag.* 201, 70–82. doi: [10.1016/j.agwat.2018.01.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2018.01.018)
- Plaza-Bonilla D, Álvaro-Fuentes J, Arrúe JL, Cantero-Martínez C 2014 Tillage and nitrogen fertilization effects on nitrous oxide yield-scaled emissions in a rainfed Mediterranean area. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 189, 43–52. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2014.03.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.03.023)
- Plaza-Bonilla D, Cantero-Martínez C, Álvaro-Fuentes J 2010 Tillage effects on soil aggregation and soil organic carbon profile distribution under Mediterranean semi-arid conditions. *Soil Use Manag.* 26, 445–474. doi: [10.1111/j.1475-2743.2010.00298.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.2010.00298.x)
- Prado P, Roque A, Pérez J, Ibáñez C, Alcaraz C et al. 2016 Warming and acidification-mediated resilience to bacterial infection determine mortality of early *Ostrea edulis* life stages. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 545, 189–202. doi: [10.3354/meps11618](https://doi.org/10.3354/meps11618)
- Range P, Piló D, Ben-Hamadou R, Chícharo MA, Matias

- D et al. 2012 Seawater acidification by CO₂ in a coastal lagoon environment: Effects on life history traits of juvenile mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. *J. Exp. Mar. Bio. Ecol.* 424–425, 89–98. doi: [10.1016/j.jembe.2012.05.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2012.05.010)
- Reguant F, Savé R 2016 Disponibilidad alimentaria y desarrollo global sostenible, in *El sistema alimentario. Globalización sostenibilidad seguridad y cultura alimentaria*, eds. Colomer-Xena Y, Clotet-Ballús R, González-Vaqué L (Thomson Reuters Proview Aranzadi).
- Requier-Desjardins M 2010 Impacts des changements climatiques sur l'agriculture au Maroc et en Tunisie et priorités d'adaptation. Notes d'Analyse du CIHEAM (56).
- Robertson GP, Paul EA, Harwood RR 2000 Greenhouse gases in intensive agriculture: Contributions of individual gases to the radiative forcing of the atmosphere. *Science (80-.)*. 289, 1922–1925. doi: [10.1126/science.289.5486.1922](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.289.5486.1922)
- Romero E, Garnier J, Billen G, Peters F, Lassaletta L 2016 Water management practices exacerbate nitrogen retention in Mediterranean catchments. *Sci. Total Environ.* 573, 420–432. doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.08.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.08.007)
- Ronco P, Zennaro F, Torresan S, Critto A, Santini M et al. 2017 A risk assessment framework for irrigated agriculture under climate change. *Adv. Water Resour.* 110, 562–578. doi: [10.1016/j.advwatres.2017.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2017.08.003)
- Ruauudel H, Morrison-Métois S 2017 Responding to Refugee Crises in Developing Countries: What Can We Learn From Evaluations? Paris. doi: [10.1787/ae4362bd-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/ae4362bd-en)
- Ryan J, de Pauw E, Gomez H, Mrabet R 2006 Drylands of the Mediterranean Zone: Biophysical Resources and Cropping Systems, in *Dryland Agriculture*, eds. Peterson G, Unger P, Payne W, 577–624.
- Saadi S, Todorovic M, Tanasijevic L, Pereira LS, Pizigalli C et al. 2015 Climate change and Mediterranean agriculture: Impacts on winter wheat and tomato crop evapotranspiration, irrigation requirements and yield. *Agric. Water Manag.* 147, 103–115. doi: [10.1016/J.AGWAT.2014.05.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AGWAT.2014.05.008)
- Saber N, Mrabet R 2002 Impact of no tillage and crop sequence on selected soil quality attributes of a vertic calcixeroll soil in Morocco. *Agronomie* 22, 451–459. doi: [10.1051/agro:2002026](https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:2002026)
- San-Miguel-Ayanz J, Moreno JM, Camia A 2013 Analysis of large fires in European Mediterranean landscapes: Lessons learned and perspectives. *For. Ecol. Manage.* 294, 11–22. doi: [10.1016/j.foreco.2012.10.050](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2012.10.050)
- Sánchez-Martín L, Meijide A, García-Torres L, Vallejo A 2010 Combination of drip irrigation and organic fertilizer for mitigating emissions of nitrogen oxides in semiarid climate. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 137, 99–107. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2010.01.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2010.01.006)
- Sánchez-Martín L, Vallejo A, Dick J, Skiba UM 2008 The influence of soluble carbon and fertilizer nitrogen on nitric oxide and nitrous oxide emissions from two contrasting agricultural soils. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 40, 142–151. doi: [10.1016/j.soilbio.2007.07.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2007.07.016)
- Santeramo FG 2015 On the composite indicators for food security: Decisions matter! *Food Rev. Int.* 31, 63–73. doi: [10.1080/87559129.2014.961076](https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2014.961076)
- Santeramo FG, Capitanio F, Adinolfi F 2014 Integrating agricultural risks management strategies in selected EU partner countries: Syria, Tunisia, Turkey. *Rom. J. Eur. Aff.* 14, 22.
- Santeramo FG, Carlucci D, de Devitiis B, Seccia A, Stasi A et al. 2018a Emerging trends in European food, diets and food industry. *Food Res. Int.* 104, 39–47. doi: [10.1016/j.foodres.2017.10.039](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.10.039)
- Santeramo FG, Cioffi A 2012 The entry price threshold in EU agriculture: Deterrent or barrier? *J. Policy Model.* 34, 691–704. doi: [10.1016/j.jpolmod.2012.02.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpolmod.2012.02.001)
- Santeramo FG, Lamonaca E 2019 On the drivers of global grain price volatility: an empirical investigation. *Agric. Econ.* 65, 31–42. doi: [10.17221/76/2018-AGRICECON](https://doi.org/10.17221/76/2018-AGRICECON)
- Santeramo FG, Lamonaca E, Contò F, Nardone G, Stasi A 2018b Drivers of grain price volatility: a cursory critical review. *Agric. Econ.* 64, 347–356. doi: [10.17221/55/2017-AGRICECON](https://doi.org/10.17221/55/2017-AGRICECON)
- Santos A, Bustamante MA, Moral R, Bernal MP 2016 Carbon conservation strategy for the management of pig slurry by composting: Initial study of the bulking agent influence. *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Chang.* 21, 1093–1105. doi: [10.1007/s11027-014-9593-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-014-9593-0)
- Sanz-Cobena A, Lassaletta L, Aguilera E, del Prado A, Garnier J et al. 2017 Strategies for greenhouse gas emissions mitigation in Mediterranean agriculture: A review. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 238, 5–24. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2016.09.038](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.09.038)
- Sanz-Cobena A, Lassaletta L, Estellés F, del Prado A, Guardia G et al. 2014 Yield-scaled mitigation of ammonia emission from N fertilization: the Spanish case. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 9, 125005. doi: [10.1088/1748-9326/9/12/125005](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/9/12/125005)
- Sanz-Cobena A, Sánchez-Martín L, García-Torres L, Vallejo A 2012 Gaseous emissions of N₂O and NO and NO₃-leaching from urea applied with urease and nitrification inhibitors to a maize (*Zea mays*) crop. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 149, 64–73. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2011.12.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.12.016)
- Savé R, de Herralde F, Aranda X, Pla E, Pascual D et al. 2012 Potential changes in irrigation requirements and phenology of maize, apple trees and alfalfa under global change conditions in Fluvia watershed during XXIst century: Results from a

- modeling approximation to watershed-level water balance. *Agric. Water Manag.* 114, 78–87. doi: [10.1016/j.agwat.2012.07.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2012.07.006)
- Saviozzi A, Levi-Minzi R, Cardelli R, Biasci A, Riffaldi R 2001 Suitability of Moist Olive Pomace as Soil Amendment. *Water, Air, Soil Pollut.* 128, 13–22. doi: [10.1023/a:1010361807181](https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1010361807181)
- Schilling J, Freier KP, Hertig E, Scheffran J 2012 Climate change, vulnerability and adaptation in North Africa with focus on Morocco. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 156, 12–26. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2012.04.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2012.04.021)
- Schils R, Olesen JE, Kersebaum KC, Rijk B, Oberforster M et al. 2018 Cereal yield gaps across Europe. *Eur. J. Agron.* 101, 109–120. doi: [10.1016/j.eja.2018.09.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2018.09.003)
- Sofi F, Abbate R, Gensini GF, Casini A 2010 Accruing evidence on benefits of adherence to the Mediterranean diet on health: an updated systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 92, 1189–1196. doi: [10.3945/ajcn.2010.29673](https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.2010.29673)
- Spinelli R, Picchi G 2010 Industrial harvesting of olive tree pruning residue for energy biomass. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101, 730–735. doi: [10.1016/j.biortech.2009.08.039](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2009.08.039)
- Sušnik J, Vamvakieridou-Lyroudia LS, Baumert N, Kloos J, Renaud FG et al. 2015 Interdisciplinary assessment of sea-level rise and climate change impacts on the lower Nile delta, Egypt. *Sci. Total Environ.* 503–504, 279–288. doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.06.111](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.06.111)
- Tanasijevic L, Todorovic M, Pereira LS, Pizzigalli C, Lionello P 2014 Impacts of climate change on olive crop evapotranspiration and irrigation requirements in the Mediterranean region. *Agric. Water Manag.* 144, 54–68. doi: [10.1016/j.agwat.2014.05.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2014.05.019)
- Tanyeri-Abur A 2015 Food Security in the southern Mediterranean/North Africa, in *The sustainability of agro-food and natural resource systems in the Mediterranean Basin.*, ed. Vastola A (Springer International Publishing), 3–14. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-16357-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16357-4)
- Thorman RE, Chadwick DR, Harrison R, Boyles LO, Matthews R 2007 The effect on N₂O emissions of storage conditions and rapid incorporation of pig and cattle farmyard manure into tillage land. *Bio-syst. Eng.* 97, 501–511. doi: [10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2007.03.039](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2007.03.039)
- Thorson G 1950 Reproductive and larval ecology of marine bottom invertebrates. *Biol. Rev. Camb. Philos. Soc.* 25, 1–45. doi: [10.1111/j.1469-185x.1950.tb00585.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185x.1950.tb00585.x)
- Toreti A, Cronie O, Zampieri M 2019 Concurrent climate extremes in the key wheat producing regions of the world. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 5493. doi: [10.1038/s41598-019-41932-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41932-5)
- Triberti L, Nastri A, Baldoni G 2016 Long-term effects of crop rotation, manure and mineral fertilisation on carbon sequestration and soil fertility. *Eur. J. Agron.* 74, 47–55. doi: [10.1016/j.eja.2015.11.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2015.11.024)
- Trnka M, Olesen JE, Kersebaum KC, Skjelvåg AO, Eitzinger J et al. 2011 Agroclimatic conditions in Europe under climate change. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 17, 2298–2318. doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02396.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02396.x)
- Tsikliras AC, Dinouli A, Tsiros V-Z, Tsalkou E 2015 The Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries at Risk from Overexploitation. *PLoS One* 10, e0121188. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0121188](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0121188)
- Tsikliras AC, Licandro P, Pardalou A, McQuinn IH, Gröger JP et al. 2019 Synchronization of Mediterranean pelagic fish populations with the North Atlantic climate variability. *Deep Sea Res. Part II Top. Stud. Oceanogr.* 159, 143–151. doi: [10.1016/j.dsr2.2018.07.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2018.07.005)
- Uddling J, Broberg MC, Feng Z, Pleijel H 2018 Crop quality under rising atmospheric CO₂. *Curr. Opin. Plant Biol.* 45, 262–267. doi: [10.1016/j.pbi.2018.06.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pbi.2018.06.001)
- Valverde P, Serralheiro R, de Carvalho M, Maia R, Oliveira B et al. 2015 Climate change impacts on irrigated agriculture in the Guadiana river basin (Portugal). *Agric. Water Manag.* 152, 17–30. doi: [10.1016/j.agwat.2014.12.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2014.12.012)
- Vergés A, Steinberg PD, Hay ME, Poore AGB, Campbell AH et al. 2014 The tropicalization of temperate marine ecosystems: climate-mediated changes in herbivory and community phase shifts. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 281, 20140846. doi: [10.1098/rspb.2014.0846](https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2014.0846)
- Verner D, Treguer DO, Redwood J, Christensen JH, McDonnell R et al. 2018 Climate variability, drought, and drought management in Morocco's agricultural sector. Washington, D.C.
- Vicente-Serrano SM, Nieto R, Gimeno L, Azorin-Molina C, Drumond A et al. 2018 Recent changes of relative humidity: regional connections with land and ocean processes. *Earth Syst. Dyn.* 9, 915–937. doi: [10.5194/esd-9-915-2018](https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-9-915-2018)
- Vicente-Serrano SM, Tomas-Burguera M, Beguería S, Reig F, Latorre B et al. 2017 A High Resolution Dataset of Drought Indices for Spain. *Data* 2, 22. doi: [10.3390/data2030022](https://doi.org/10.3390/data2030022)
- Vicente-Vicente JL, García-Ruiz R, Francaviglia R, Aguilera E, Smith P 2016 Soil carbon sequestration rates under Mediterranean woody crops using recommended management practices: A meta-analysis. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 235, 204–214. doi: [10.1016/j.agee.2016.10.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.10.024)
- Vincent-Cabou L, Peigné J, Casagrande M, Silva E 2017 Overview of Organic Cover Crop-Based No-Tillage Technique in Europe: Farmers' Practices and Research Challenges. *Agriculture* 7, 42. doi: [10.3390/agriculture7050042](https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture7050042)
- Waha K, Krümmenauer L, Adams S, Aich V, Baarsch F

- et al. 2017 Climate change impacts in the Middle East and Northern Africa (MENA) region and their implications for vulnerable population groups. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 17, 1623–1638. doi: [10.1007/s10113-017-1144-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-017-1144-2)
- Webb J, Chadwick DR, Ellis S 2004 Emissions of ammonia and nitrous oxide following incorporation into the soil of farmyard manures stored at different densities. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosystems* 70, 67–76. doi: [10.1023/b:fres.0000045985.32440.27](https://doi.org/10.1023/b:fres.0000045985.32440.27)
- Webber H, Ewert F, Olesen JE, Müller C, Fronzek S et al. 2018 Diverging importance of drought stress for maize and winter wheat in Europe. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 4249. doi: [10.1038/s41467-018-06525-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-06525-2)
- Zampieri M, Ceglar A, Dentener FJ, Dosio A, Naumann G et al. 2019 When will current climate extremes affecting maize production become the norm? *Earth's Futur.* 7, 113–122. doi: [10.1029/2018ef000995](https://doi.org/10.1029/2018ef000995)
- Zampieri M, Ceglar A, Dentener FJ, Toreti A 2017 Wheat yield loss attributable to heat waves, drought and water excess at the global, national and subnational scales. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 12, 064008. doi: [10.1088/1748-9326/aa723b](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa723b)
- Zampieri M, Toreti A, Ceglar A, Naumann G, Turco M et al. 2020 Climate resilience of the top ten wheat producers in the Mediterranean and the Middle East. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 20, 41. doi: [10.1007/s10113-020-01622-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-020-01622-9)

Information about authors

Coordinating Lead Authors

Rachid Mrabet:

National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA Morocco), Rabat, Morocco

Robert Savé:

Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA), Caldes de Montbui (Barcelona), Spain

Lead Authors

Nuno Caiola:

Climate Change department, Technology Centre of Catalonia, EURECAT, Spain

Mouad Chentouf:

National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA Morocco), Tangier, Morocco

Llasat Maria Carmen:

University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

Assem Abdelmonem Ahmed Mohamed:

Agricultural Research Center (ARC), Central Laboratory for Agricultural Climate (CLAC), Giza, Egypt

Fabio G. Santeramo:

University of Foggia, Foggia, Italy

Alberto Sanz-Cobeña:

CEIGRAM, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Madrid, Spain

Andrea Toreti:

European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Ispra, Italy

Athanosios Tsikliras:

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

Contributing Authors

Eduardo Aguilera:

CEIGRAM, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Madrid, Spain

Luis Asin:

Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA), Lleida, Spain

Alejandro Blas:

CEIGRAM, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Madrid, Spain

Andrej Ceglar:

European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Ispra, Italy

Donna Dimarchopoulou:

University of Rhode Island, United States of America

Elena Georgopoulou:

National Observatory of Athens, Athens, Greece

Luis Lassaletta:

CEIGRAM, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Madrid, Spain

Androniki Pardalou:

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

Giuseppe Scarcella:

National Research Council, Institute of Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnologies (CNR-IRBIM), Ancona, Italy

Marco Turco:

University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

Matteo Zampieri:

European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Ispra, Italy